

Impact of elevated temperature on the Giant magnetoimpedance effect in Co-rich glass-coated microwires

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ABSTRACT

We studied the giant magnetoimpedance, GMI, effect in as-prepared and current annealed $\text{Co}_{72}\text{Fe}_4\text{B}_{13}\text{Si}_{11}$ glass-coated microwires at ambient and elevated temperatures. We observed an increase in the GMI ratio, $\Delta Z/Z$, with an increase in the measurement temperature up to 100 °C, followed by a considerable decrease of its values above 100 °C until its complete disappearance at the Curie temperature. A remarkable increase in $\Delta Z/Z$ up to 900 % is observed at 100 °C, while the magnetic field sensitivity up to 14 %/(A/m) has been experimentally recorded. Observed changes are reversible up to 100 °C, but past it, some irreversible changes to hysteresis loops and GMI effect are documented, such as transformation of hysteresis loops shape from almost linear to rectangular, and transition in the $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies from double-peak to almost single-peak. The origins of these changes in magnetic properties are discussed in terms of temperature dependence and the relaxation of internal stresses.

Unusual magnetic properties of magnetic wires linked to their cylindrical symmetry have attracted attention for several decades [1,2]. However, in the case of wires with crystalline structure, these properties are substantially influenced by structural defects, such as dislocations, grain boundaries, twins, textures, etc.... [3]. However, in amorphous materials with glass-like structure, the influence of such defects can be suppressed (although the effects of clusters or short range atomic ordering cannot be completely avoided) [4]. Therefore, development of amorphous materials technologies during the 80's ushered in a new era in the research of magnetic properties of magnetic amorphous wires, mainly due to their good magnetic softness combined with superior mechanical and corrosion resistance properties [5–8]. In particular, studies of the Giant Magnetoimpedance (GMI) effect, initially discovered in Permalloy wires and then reported in amorphous Co-rich wires and ribbons, gained special attention owing to strong sensitivity of the impedance, Z , of soft magnetic conductors to an applied magnetic field, H . The origin of the GMI effect is satisfactorily explained in terms of

changes to the skin depth, δ , of the AC current traversing through a magnetically soft conductor under the influence of an applied magnetic field, H , given as [1,9,10]:

$$\delta = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi\sigma f\mu_{\phi}}} \quad (1)$$

being σ -the electrical conductivity, f -the frequency of the AC and μ_{ϕ} -the circumferential magnetic permeability. Accordingly, a high GMI effect is linked to a substantial $\mu_{\phi}(H)$ dependence [1,9,10].

In most publications, to better visualize it, the magnitude of the GMI effect is expressed in terms of the so-called GMI ratio, $\Delta Z/Z$, defined as [9,10]:

$$\Delta Z/Z = 100 \cdot [Z(H) - Z(H_{max})]/Z(H_{max}) \quad (2)$$

where H_{max} is the maximum applied DC magnetic field (typically below a few kA/m).

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Typically, maximum values of $\Delta Z/Z \approx 300\%$ are reported in Co-rich magnetic wires, which also present the best magnetic softness owing to their vanishing magnetostriction coefficient, λ_s [3,9,10]. It is worth noting that $\Delta Z/Z$ – values of up to 700% were experimentally observed in carefully processed glass-coated Co-rich amorphous microwires [11–13] or in Co-rich melt extracted magnetic microwires [14]. However, while these are good improvements in GMI performance, they are still far away from the rather higher $\Delta Z/Z \approx 3000\%$ that has been theoretically predicted [15].

Lately, in an attempt to try and reach that theoretical maximum, research on glass-coated microwires has attracted attention due to a unique combination of their properties, which include remarkable magnetic softness, higher observed GMI effect, and excellent mechanical properties [6,16], that make them highly suitable for various sensing applications. Additionally, their flexible, insulating glass-coating provides even better corrosion resistance and allows for biocompatibility, making these microwires suitable for emerging novel applications, like in biomedicine, or stress monitoring in civil engineering and/or aircraft industry using them as magnetic inclusions in smart composites [17–20]. A simple method to prepare glass-coated microwires, and the one used in this work, is the Taylor-Ulitovsky technique, consisting of the simultaneous quenching of molten metal and glass, pulled directly from the melt of a metallic alloy inside a glass capillary, as seen in Fig. 1a [3,21,22]. As discussed elsewhere, the main source of magnetic anisotropy in amorphous materials is linked to the magnetoelastic contribution [4] and, therefore, to the internal stresses originated mostly by the simultaneous quenching and solidification of metallic alloy and glass coating with different thermal expansion coefficients, and the interaction of these stresses with the λ_s -value, making them the main factors limiting both magnetic softness and $\Delta Z/Z$ – values [3,11–13]. The use of

Co-rich alloys doped with Fe or Mn, (i.e. $\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_x$ or $\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Mn}_x$ with $0.03 \leq x \leq 0.08$) has shown to achieve vanishing λ_s -values ($\lambda_s \sim 10^{-7}$), while annealing has become a common route to relax the internal stresses to tune magnetic properties of microwires, further enhancing them after fabrication [3].

One of the most prospective applications of glass-coated microwires is monitoring of external stimuli (magnetic field, temperature changes, mechanical stress...) employing magnetic wire inclusions in composites through the use of free space microwave spectroscopy [19,20,23–25]. This technique involves the dependence of the effective permittivity, ϵ_{eff} , on the wires' impedance, Z , which, in turn, is linked to the sensitivity of Z - to external stimuli, such as applied stress, temperature or magnetic field. Among them, the stress monitoring has become the studied, with many publications on the influence of applied stress on GMI effect and even on the stress-impedance effect being published [26–29]. However, the temperature, T , dependence of the GMI effect is comparatively poorly studied, with most of studies related to this field carried out on different amorphous materials (ribbons or thick magnetic wires without glass coating), with quite narrow temperature ranges [30–32], leaving temperature dependence of GMI effect of glass-coated microwires poorly studied.

A novel experimental facility recently developed by the Institute of Experimental Physics of Kosice (SAS) allowed to substantially extend the temperature range for GMI measurements, which was used to obtain substantial dependences of $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ –values with temperature in Fe-rich and Co-rich amorphous microwires [33–35].

In this paper we provide our latest experimental results on the temperature dependence of the GMI effect in as-prepared and annealed $\text{Co}_{72}\text{Fe}_4\text{B}_{13}\text{Si}_{11}$ glass-coated microwires with metallic nucleus diameter, d , of $41.1\ \mu\text{m}$ and total microwire diameter, D , of $44.5\ \mu\text{m}$, as we recently reported an improved maximum GMI ratio of 730% on them upon annealing [13]. The interest on this specific microwire comes from its elevated diameter, as it was successfully produced with amorphous structure using the Taylor-Ulitovsky technique despite its usual difficulty at fabricating larger microwires.

The GMI effect was measured at temperatures, T , ranging from ambient temperature up to $300\ \text{°C}$, at selected frequencies, f , up to 110 MHz. Additionally, using the calculated GMI ratios, we evaluated their magnetic field sensitivity, η , expressed as [13]:

$$\eta(H) = \frac{\partial \left(\frac{\Delta Z}{Z} \right)}{\partial H} \quad (3)$$

The amorphous structure of the as-prepared and annealed microwires was confirmed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) (see Fig. 1b), confirming that crystallization of these microwires is not observed to occur even after 3 h at $>300\ \text{°C}$. Additionally, the crystallization of these Co-rich microwires is being typically observed after annealing at temperature, T_{ann} , above $500\ \text{°C}$ (for 60 min). This means that the observed changes in magnetic properties of studied microwires in this work should not be attributed to crystallization of the metallic nucleus under high temperatures, as it is observed to not happen at these temperature and time ranges. The vanishing, negative magnetostriction coefficient, λ_s , of as-prepared sample ($\lambda_s \approx -0.3 \times 10^{-6}$) was also previously obtained using the small angle magnetization rotation (SAMR) method [13,36].

For Joule heating, we used a simple setup consisting of a direct electrical circuit, connecting both ends of each 12 cm long microwire sample to a direct current generator set to apply the desired current intensity for a set time period, allowing for sample heating in the presence of a circular magnetic field induced by the electrical current inside the metallic nucleus [37]. When selecting the annealing conditions (DC current value and time periods), we have considered that the crystallization of studied samples happens at $T > 500\ \text{°C}$ (Fig. 1b). It was previously demonstrated that Joule heating performed at current densities, j , of around $30\text{--}45\ \text{A/mm}^2$ produces a heating equivalent to $400\ \text{°C}$ [38]. Theoretically, similar temperatures were obtained for other glass-coated

Fig. 1. Image of the experimental setup for glass-coated microwires fabrication (a) and XRD pattern of as-prepared and annealed at $370\ \text{°C}$ microwire (b).

microwires ($d = 18 \mu\text{m}$) annealed at $I \approx 30 \text{ mA}$ [39]. In addition, it has been experimentally demonstrated (by magnetic hardening and by drop in the electrical resistivity) and then confirmed through a rigorous assessment, taking into account convection and radiative heat transfer, that crystallization of glass-coated microwires begins for current densities of $j > 200 \text{ A/mm}^2$ [38–40]. In our experiments, the used I -values (below 70 mA) correspond to $j \leq 15 \text{ A/mm}^2$, which are clearly below $j \approx 200 \text{ A/mm}^2$, thus avoiding any significant crystallization [38,39]. To complement these previous results, the Curie temperature of as-prepared microwire was evaluated from the temperature dependence of magnetization, measured using a Physical Property Magnetic System, PPMS. From the dependence of magnetic moment, M , on temperature, as seen in Fig. 2a, we evaluate the Curie temperature, T_c , of the sample as $T_c \approx 265 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The slight increase of the M -values at $T > 500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ must be related with the precipitation of crystalline ferromagnetic phases.

Before starting the GMI studies, we measured the hysteresis loops of the samples at room temperature using the fluxmetric method, which was previously successfully used for the characterization of extremely soft magnetic microwires [3,13,36]. The hysteresis loops are presented as the magnetic field, H , dependence of the normalized magnetization, $M/M_0(H)$ (where M - the magnetic moment at a given H -value and M_0 - the magnetic moment of studied sample and at maximum magnetic field amplitude, H_m). Low-field hysteresis loops of studied samples, as-prepared and Joule heated at $I = 70 \text{ mA}$ for 20 min, measured at room temperature are shown in Fig. 2b,c. As can be observed, both microwire samples present rather good soft magnetic properties with coercivities, H_c , of about 30 A/m (as-prepared) and 27 A/m (after Joule heating) and magnetic anisotropy fields, H_k , of about 145 A/m and 130 A/m respectively, showing that employed Joule heating allows for a slight improvement of the magnetic softness.

The $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies measured at $f = 40 \text{ MHz}$ at room temperature of as-prepared and annealed samples are shown in Fig. 3a. Among the most relevant points is a quite high maximum GMI ratio, $\Delta Z/Z$

Fig. 2. $M(T)$ dependence of as-prepared sample (a) and hysteresis loops of studied as-prepared (b), after Joule heating at 70 mA for 20 min (c) samples.

Fig. 3. $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependences of as-prepared and annealed (Joule heating at 70 mA for 20 min) (a), and $\Delta Z/Z_m(f)$ dependence for the same samples (b).

Z_m , of about 700 % observed in as-prepared sample, which, as mentioned before, is even further enhanced up to 780 % after application of Joule heating. To illustrate the extent of this enhancement, Fig. 3b represents the $\Delta Z/Z_m(f)$ dependence, showing that the annealed sample presents a consistently higher GMI ratio, and that this effect is observed to be the highest at $f = 40 \text{ MHz}$ (which is what motivates that future $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies in this work will be shown at 40 MHz). The double-peak character present in all measured $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies were previously experimentally observed and linked to the circumferential character of the magnetic anisotropy of the magnetic wires with low and negative λ_s -values [9,41].

After having characterized the GMI effect at room temperature, and the effects that Joule heating has on it, we move on to study these aspects at different temperatures, as shown in Fig. 4a, b. A steady increase in $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values can be appreciated in both as-prepared and Joule heated samples as temperature rises up to $T = 100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, which is then followed by a substantial decrease until, at $300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the GMI effect has practically disappeared ($\Delta Z/Z_m \approx 0$), in agreement with the observed Curie temperature, as seen in Fig. 2a, $T_c \approx 265 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. However, before this loss of the GMI effect there is a remarkable note to be made as, at $T = 100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the annealed sample exhibits quite high $\Delta Z/Z$ -values, up to 900 % (see Fig. 4b). Accordingly, the magnetic field sensitivity, η , evaluated from that $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependence achieves values up to $\eta \approx 14 \text{ } \%/(\text{A/m})$ (see Fig. 4c).

Another relevant feature observed in Fig. 3, 4a and b is a gradual modification in the character of the $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies upon heating: as T increases, the magnetic field, H_m , corresponding to $\Delta Z/Z_m$, which is associated with the magnetic anisotropy field of microwires at MHz frequencies [9,41], shifts to lower H_m -values. Thus, observed changes in $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies should be indicative of a change in magnetic anisotropy as temperature rises. As recently discussed [42], variations of magnetic properties and GMI effect with temperature can be explained in terms of internal stresses, σ_i , specifically on their dependence on temperature and relaxation, as we previously confirmed the amorphous nature of the structure of the microwire before and after exposure to these temperatures (Fig. 1a). The difference between these contributions is that the $\sigma_i(T)$ dependence should present a reversible character, while relaxation of internal stresses is expected to produce irreversible changes of magnetic properties.

Hysteresis loops measured at ambient temperature after exposure to

Fig. 4. $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies measured at $f = 40$ MHz at different T of microwire as-prepared (1), and annealed (Joule heating at 70 mA for 20 min) (b) and $\eta(H)$ dependence for as-prepared and annealed samples at ambient temperature (RT) and at $T = 100$ °C (c).

100 °C and 300 °C are provided in Fig. 5a. While the hysteresis loop measured after heating up to $T = 100$ °C remains almost unchanged, a substantial change in loop shape, from almost linear to rectangular, is observed after heating up to $T = 300$ °C (see Fig. 5a). These changes in the hysteresis loops correlate with the change in shape of $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies, while $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -value remain almost unmodified in both cases. Additionally, a substantial decrease in H_m -value is observed after exposure to 300 °C (see Fig. 5b). In contrast, the $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependence measured after the heating up to 100 °C remains almost unchanged:

both $\Delta Z/Z_m$ and H_m -values (see Fig. 5b).

The evolution of $\Delta Z/Z_m$ and H_m -values with temperature is provided in Fig. 5c and d. While the annealed sample presents higher values of $\Delta Z/Z_m$, the character of $\Delta Z/Z_m(T)$ dependence is almost the same in both samples: a substantial increase of $\Delta Z/Z_m$ up to 100 °C followed by a decrease at higher temperatures (see Fig. 5c). Regarding $H_m(T)$, the observed influence of temperature on H_m is similar to that recently observed on different Co-rich microwires: again an almost linear decrease up to 100 °C followed by mostly temperature independent

Fig. 5. Hysteresis loops measured at ambient temperature in as-prepared sample and sample after heating to 100 °C and 300 °C (a), $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependences of as-prepared sample and after heating to 300 °C (b), $\Delta Z/Z_m(T)$ (c) and $H_m(T)$ (d) dependencies of both samples.

H_m -values at higher temperatures [34,42]. This behaviour can be explained by recalling the influence of magnetoelastic anisotropy on magnetic properties of amorphous microwires. The internal stresses are mainly originated by the difference between glass and metallic alloy's thermal expansion coefficients, α_m and α_g , when the materials cool down and solidify simultaneously. As this happens while the microwire is being pulled on by the drawing mechanism, the main component of these internal stresses is usually the axial one, resulting, therefore, in axial magnetic anisotropy for glass-coated microwires with positive λ_s , and transverse magnetic anisotropy for those with negative λ_s [43–46]. Given the relevance of internal stresses on the microwire's magnetic behaviour, it is no wonder that modifications of the magnetic anisotropy field, H_k , upon application of tensile stress, σ , were experimentally observed [47]. The relationship between H_k and σ is explained by the $\lambda_s(\sigma)$ dependence, experimentally observed in amorphous alloys with low and negative λ_s , described as [48]:

$$\lambda_{s,\sigma} = \lambda_{s,0} - B\sigma \quad (4)$$

where $\lambda_{s,\sigma}$ is the magnetostriction coefficient at a given σ , $\lambda_{s,0}$ is the magnetostriction coefficient at $\sigma = 0$ and B is a positive coefficient of order 10^{-10} MPa.

Considering the almost reversible behaviour of hysteresis loops observed at temperatures up to 100 °C and the analysis of temperature dependence of the magnetic properties and GMI effect in our recent

publications, we can propose that the reversible behaviour at $T \leq 100$ °C can be related to a $\sigma_i(T)$ dependence. In previous publications this dependence was described as [32]:

$$\sigma_i \approx E(\alpha_g - \alpha_m) / T \quad (5)$$

where E is the Young modulus, and α_g and α_m are the thermal expansion coefficients of glass and metallic nucleus, respectively.

Accordingly, the monotonic, almost linear $H_m(T)$ dependencies up to 100 °C (Fig. 5d) can be attributed to the reversible contribution of temperature dependence of internal stresses. On the other hand, changes in H_m , hysteresis loops and GMI effect observed at $T > 100$ °C must be related to irreversible internal stresses relaxation, and the corresponding changes in domain structure, in addition to possible short range atomic reordering. Resuming, we observed a remarkable temperature dependence of the GMI effect in as-prepared and annealed $\text{Co}_{72}\text{Fe}_4\text{B}_{13}\text{Si}_{11}$ glass-coated microwires with diameters of $d = 41.1$ μm and $D = 45$ μm . In their as-prepared state, these microwires already show quite high GMI effect of 700 %, which is successfully enhanced via Joule heating, up to 780 %. Under the influence of heating, until about 100 °C, we experimentally observed growth in the GMI ratio of both as prepared and current annealed samples. While both samples exhibited a remarkable growth in GMI efficiency, the Joule heated sample experimented a larger enhancement with temperature, of the order of 900 %, with a remarkable magnetic field sensitivity up to ~ 14 %/(A/m), whereas the as-

prepared sample only reached a ratio of ~ 800 % with sensitivity of ~ 10 %/(A/m). At heating above 100 °C, the GMI effect on both samples progressively diminishes, until it disappears at T values above the Curie temperature, 265 °C.

Observed temperature dependences are reversible up to about 100 °C, while above this, irreversible changes in hysteresis loops and GMI effect are observed in studied samples. Thus, the magnetic hardening indicated by the hysteresis loop transformation from inclined to square upon heating must be correlated to the change in $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies from double-peak to almost single-peak dependence that are observed after reaching high enough temperatures. The origin of the observed temperature dependences is discussed in terms of the temperature dependence of internal stresses and their relaxation.

Data availability

The raw/processed data required to reproduce these findings cannot be shared at this time as the data also forms part of an ongoing study.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

A. Gonzalez: Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **I. Skorvanek:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **M. Jakubcin:** Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **V. Zhukova:** Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Resources, Funding acquisition. **A. Zhukov:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors of the manuscript “Impact of elevated temperature on the Giant magnetoimpedance effect in Co-rich glass-coated microwires” by A. Gonzalez, I. Skorvanek, M. Jakubcin, V. Zhukova and A. Zhukov declare no competing financial or/and non-financial interests.

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Supplementary materials

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